

Polarographic Study of Methoxyethyl Thioglycolate Complexes of Cadmium

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The composition and the stability constants of Cd-Methoxyethyl Thioglycolate complexes were evaluated by measuring the shift in the polarographic half wave reduction potential of Cd^{+2} as a function of methoxyethyl thioglycolate concentration employing De Ford and Hume's method. The ionic species found to exist in solutions of constant ionic strength ($\mu = 0.5$) at 25° were CdA^+ , CdA_2 , CdA_3^- . The logarithms of the stability constants at 25° were found to be 7.50, 8.90, 10.90 respectively.

Thiols and chelate ligands containing thiol groups belong to a very important class of organic compounds. They provide different possible coordination sites viz. $-\text{SH}$, $-\text{COOH}$, $-\text{OH}$ groups etc. and can act as mono, bi, and tridentate. Being highly polarizable, sulphhydryl group forms strong bonds with heavy metal ions and show interesting behaviour towards complex formation. The polarographic behaviour of thiomalic acid, β -mercaptopropionic acid, thiolactic acid, 3-Mercapto 1, 2- Propanediol, etc., and their complexes¹⁻⁹ with metals have already been studied in these laboratories by Saxena and co-workers. There is, however, no reference in the literature regarding the metal complexes on methoxyethyl thioglycolate and their stability constants and hence the present investigation has been undertaken.

EXPERIMENTAL

Reagents : Methoxyethyl thioglycolate was supplied by Evans Chemetics, Inc., New York, carrying 98%. All other chemicals were of reagent grade and were used without further purification. Their solutions were prepared in doubly distilled air-free conductivity water. Freshly prepared solutions were always used to avoid the effects of ageing and air oxidation. Triton X-100 (0.001%) was used as maximum suppressor. The ionic strength was maintained at 0.5 M by adding requisite amount of NaClO_4 .

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Apparatus : A Cambridge (G.P.) polarograph in conjunction with thermostated H-cell was used for recording C-V curves. An external saturated calomel electrode connected to the cell by means of an agar salt bridge served as reference electrode. Capillary had the following characteristics measured in 0.5M NaClO₄, $m = 1.462$ mg/sec, $t = 3.45$ secs. (VS S.C.E.). Dissolved air was removed from the solution by bubbling oxygen free nitrogen through the cell and a complete inert atmosphere was maintained over the solution during the electrolysis. Doubly distilled mercury was used for the dropping mercury electrode. Unless otherwise stated all measurements were done with the polarographic cell immersed in a thermostated bath controlled at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

Procedure : To investigate the reversibility and diffusion controlled nature of the cathodic wave produced by Cd⁺² in methoxyethyl thioglycolate media, the concentration of Cd⁺² and the effect of change of mercury head on wave heights were studied. For complexation studies, a series of 0.4 mM CdSO₄ solutions containing varying concentrations (.01M to .05M) of methoxyethyl thioglycolate and 0.001% Triton-X were prepared. Requisite amounts of NaClO₄ was added to maintain the ionic strength at 0.5M. Polarograms of deoxygenated solutions were recorded. Half wave potentials were obtained from plots of $E_{d.e.}$ vs. $\log \frac{i}{(i_d - i)}$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The plots of $\log i/(i_d - i)$ vs. voltage for all polarograms yielded straight lines having slopes in agreement with the theoretical value, the mean slope for the series was 0.0308, indicating that the complex species reduce reversibly. The plot of i_d vs. $h_{eff}^{\frac{1}{2}}$ was found to be linear and pass through the origin, indicating the diffusion controlled nature of the wave. The appreciable difference in the diffusion currents of Cd⁺² ion alone and in the presence of methoxyethyl thioglycolate indicate that aquo cadmium ion and Cd-Methoxyethyl thioglycolate complex differ in size. Half wave potential values, evaluated from the log plots, were found to shift towards more negative values with increasing methoxyethyl thioglycolate concentration indicating complexation between Cd²⁺ and methoxyethyl thioglycolate. The plot of $E_{1/2}$ as a function of log of methoxyethyl thioglycolate concentration showed curvature indicating the formation of successive complexes.

De Ford and Hume¹⁰ have derived the necessary equations for calculation of the stability constants of consecutive complexes, for the reversible polarographic reduction of a complexed metal ion to the metal amalgam

They have defined functions, $F_j(X)$, such that

$$F_0(X) = \text{antilog} \left\{ 0.435 \frac{nE'}{RT} [(E_{1/2})_s^\circ - (E_{1/2})_c^\circ] + \log \frac{I_s}{I_c} \right\} \quad (2)$$

$$F_1(X) = [F_0(X) - (\beta_0/f_s)]/C_x f_x \quad (3)$$

$$F_2(X) = [F_1(X) - (\beta_{1/fm_x})]/C_x f_x \quad (4)$$

etc.

$(E_{1/2})_0^\circ$ and $(E_{1/2})_c^\circ$ are the half wave potentials for the uncomplexed and complexed metal ions respectively. I_0 and I_c are the diffusion current constants for the same species. The formation constant of the zero complex β_0 is defined as unity; f_0 and f_x are the activity coefficients of the uncomplexed metal and the ligand, and C_x is the concentration of the latter. β_1 is the stability constant of 1 : 1 complex, and f_{m_x} the activity coefficient of the complex.

When a plot is made of $F_j(X)$ vs. $C_x f_x$ and extrapolated to $C_x = 0$, the intercept is equal to β_j/f_{m_x} . The activity coefficients may be equated to unity as the ionic strength is maintained constant to keep the same ionic atmosphere throughout the series of measurements.¹¹

Plots of $F_0(X)$, $F_1(X)$, $F_2(X)$ and $F_3(X)$ vs. ligand concentration have been shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2. Extrapolation of these curves to $C_x = 0$ gives the values of stability constants which are found to be $\beta_1 = 3.5 \times 10^7$, $\beta_2 = 7.5 \times 10^8$ and $\beta_3 = 8.0 \times 10^{10}$.

Fig. 1. Plot of $E_{1/2}$ vs. $\log C_x$ for Cd-Methoxyethyl Thioglycolate system.

Fig. 2. Values of $F_0(X)$ and $F_1(X)$ for Cadmium in Methoxyethyl Thioglycolate solutions [(O) $F_0(X)$ (●) $F_1(X)$.]

The plot of $F_3(X)$ vs ligand concentration showed a horizontal line indicating the formation of only three complexes. As a check on the values for β_2 and β_3 , the limiting slopes were obtained; which approximate the values for the next higher complex.¹⁰ The limiting slope for the $F_1(X)$ curve was calculated as 7.65×10^8 ($\beta_2 = 7.50 \times 10^8$) and for the $F_2(X)$ curve as 8.12×10^{10} ($\beta_3 = 8.0 \times 10^{10}$).

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The data obtained on the Cd^{+2} -Methoxyethyl thioglycolate system show (i) three complexes CdA^+ , CdA_2 and CdA_3^- are formed, (ii) the logarithim values of stability constants are found to be $\log \beta_1 = 7.50$, $\log \beta_2 = 8.90$ and $\log \beta_3 = 10.90$, (iii) the reduction of Cd^{+2} in methoxyethyl thioglycolate solution is reversible and diffusion controlled and hence cadmium can be determined polarographically in methoxyethyl thioglycolate media.

Fig. 3. Values of $F_2(X)$ and $F_3(X)$ are cadmium in Methoxyethyl Thioglycolate solutions. [(O) $F_2(X)$; (●) $F_3(X)$.]

TABLE I

Solution No.	C_x moles/lit.	$-E_{1/2}$ (v)	i_d (μA)	$F_0(X)$	$F_1(X)$	$F_2(X)$	$F_3(X)$
1	0.0	0.625	8.90	—	—	—	—
2	0.01	0.820	7.15	5.03×10^5	5.02×10^7	1.53×10^9	7.8×10^{10}
3	0.02	0.835	7.05	16.44×10^5	8.22×10^7	2.35×10^9	8.1×10^{10}
4	0.03	0.846	6.95	39.34×10^5	13.11×10^7	3.20×10^9	8.1×10^{10}
5	0.04	0.855	7.15	77.18×10^5	19.29×10^7	3.39×10^9	8.0×10^{10}
6	0.05	0.860	7.05	115.60×10^5	23.12×10^7	3.93×10^9	6.3×10^{10}
				$\beta_1 = 3.5 \times 10^7$	$\beta_2 = 7.5 \times 10^8$	$\beta_3 = 8.0 \times 10^{10}$	

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